

HOTAGOGIA AMONG EDUCATIONAL LEADERS AT JORDANIAN UNIVERSITIES: SUGGESTIONS FOR DEVELOPMENT AND STIMULATION

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Abstract

The study's objective was to identify the theologies of educational leaders at Jordanian institutions and make suggestions for activating and improving them. Twenty faculty members from Jordanian universities were interviewed as part of the study's qualitative methodology. The findings of these interviews revealed that the educational leaders made five recommendations to enhance and enliven their theologies at Jordanian institutions. These included implementing measures to enhance the fundamental competencies and untapped potential of all educational administrators in the university-based educational system, implementing cutting-edge techniques, and emphasizing the significance of ability and self-discovery. The principle of Hotagogia is intended to be used by educational leaders as one of the modern learning methods. Jordanian universities give educational leaders the freedom to learn by selecting the method that is best for them, and they aim to spread the culture of Hotagogia among educational leaders and all employees in Jordanian universities. More research on Hotagogia should be done in Jordanian universities, and it should be linked to other factors, according to the study's recommendations.

Keywords: Hotagogia, educational leaders, Jordanian universities

INTRODUCTION

As educational leaders in universities are regarded as an important resource due to their role in universities achieving their current and future goals, which necessitates them to always strive for development, universities play a fundamental role in spreading science and knowledge in the various educational circles by keeping up with recent developments that have occurred throughout history. The term "Hotagogia" is used by scientists and historians to describe this process by which people try to better themselves, their abilities, and their talents.

Universities aim to use Hotagogia and apply it to all employees within their departments and administrative and organizational structures in all areas of work, support employees, and create the right environment in order to practice Hotagogia because it is a starting point for development, creativity, achievement, and excellence (Natalia, 2016), being an indicator of the degree of success achieved by individuals in universities, the degree of which means that educational leaders have to keep up with changes in education and improve themselves. Then, the strategic plans and methods have to be carried out according to the goals set, and they have to be planned in a way that meets the general requirements in universities and fulfils the vision and mission of universities. This is good for the growth, development, and prosperity of universities and the whole country.

The term Hotagogia has attracted a lot of attention from educational researchers in the field of education because it provides an explanation of self-learning based on experience and firsthand knowledge. The individual goes through all stages of his personal, social, and practical life by developing this concept in order to benefit from it in all facets of his life. A fundamental demand for people that they must fulfil in order to improve their knowledge and skill sets and then apply what they have learned in their varied life experiences and contexts (Al-Qasim, 2018).

The idea of Hotagogia supports educational leaders by streamlining individual and group processes, assisting in decision-making, and allowing leaders to plan effectively and efficiently to capitalize on the demands of change occurring in university work environments and to achieve quality in accordance with high standards that keep up with the most recent advancements. Achieving integration between university functions in the provision of creative services, strengthening knowledge management, and opening new channels of communication between all stakeholders in the educational process inside and outside universities will help it keep up with changes and developments (Maree, 2016).

Since university leaders play an important and significant role in the success of universities and the accomplishment of their current and future goals, they have a propensity to introduce radical changes to the educational system in universities and raise their level of innovation.

Educational leaders in universities therefore seek to keep up with everything new in order to move away from the usual routine practices. To improve the teaching and learning processes and achieve a high level of effective self-learning, leadership development is one of the things that must be focused on, cared for, and looked at in a meaningful way. This is because the educational process includes administrative, educational, and organizational systems and structures (Gabbour, 2015). Since it interacts with and is influenced by everything around it, all of the significant components that play an active part in achieving the objectives and outcomes set forth by a continuous education system are fundamental to building and developing the educational system (Al-Qahtani, 2020).

Challenges in the educational field were observed by looking at the reality of Jordanian universities, and there is no doubt that resistance to change is one of the most significant barriers that emerge in university work environments and that educational leaders in universities face. There is also an urgent need for self-learning in order to keep up with the rapid developments and address the fundamental needs that you have. Leaders during their educational practices in universities, skill gaps, disparities in the capabilities and expertise of educational leaders, slackness in all work environments, abuse of legislation, regulations, and laws, creation of administrative and societal barriers that are inconsistent with prevailing ethical standards in the university and local community, and deviation from the proper course of business are all examples of leaders during their educational practices. This study was conducted to shed light on the Hotagogia of educational leaders in Jordanian universities and provide suggestions for improvement and activation. Universities are places where the best values are disintegrating, and there are numerous local, regional, and international challenges. This indicates the importance of the subject and that we are on the cusp of a new world, especially given the current trend towards globalization.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Educational leaders in universities began to practice their work within the educational goals that each of them is aware of striving to achieve, in order to work on developing skills and enhancing them in the right way, which helps universities towards achieving their current goals and future aspirations and ensuring their success and performance with excellence and creativity, and a distinguished educational leader has the ability To discover and enhance the latent energies, and the university environment has a role in raising the levels of performance of educational leaders as it contributes to providing good conditions and a suitable climate for improving their performance, and motivates them towards appropriate and appropriate work for the general educational goals.

Hotagogia was defined as: “the methods by which the individual himself uses various educational situations to acquire information and skills, so that the focus of attention shifts from the teacher to the learner, so that he becomes responsible for his learning and for making his cultural and knowledge progress, and for the results and decisions he takes” (Saada and Ibrahim, 17, 2020).

As Al-Satoori defined it (2020, 40). It is: "an individual's skill or his own method of self-learning, which differs from one person to another, and is according to the capabilities of the individual himself in obtaining knowledge, based on choosing the appropriate methods and effective strategy for learning." The researcher also concludes that the Hotagogia is self-learning by the individual stemming from within the individual and the extent of his passion and motivation to develop his skills and abilities and increase his experiences and invest them in a way that serves all individuals in society.

Significance of Hotagogia

Hotagogia is regarded as one of the primary gateways to individual and professional growth in all professions, owing to the individual's effort to pursue growth, development, and rejuvenation. With peers in the workplace and outside of it (Hamadat, 2014), and Hotagogia is important in increasing the individual's active learning, as he is always ready to receive new knowledge and develop and develop his skills in a positive way, which is reflected in universities in properly preparing individuals with the ability to face challenges and pressures. Work, and that they are accountable to themselves, their employers, and society in order to attain their objectives (Chika, 2015).

The aims of Hotagogia

Al-Rawaf (2002) tracked numerous **Hotagogia** goals, including:

- Individual mastery of the basic and necessary abilities that he will need along his life path.
- Developing individuals with a sense of group responsibility and affiliation with successful community institutions.
- Encouraging individuals to explore and develop themselves in accordance with the needs of the current era.
- Educating the individual on how to confront, solve, and overcome challenges and difficulties.
- Providing an appropriate educational environment for the individual in where creativity and achievement reign supreme.

Hotagogia criteria

Hajji (2000) mentioned a list of parameters on which Hotagogia is founded, which include:

- Emphasizing individual differences: because each member of society has characteristics, characteristics, and characteristics that distinguish them from others and express their tendencies, desires, and needs that the individual requires in his educational environment, and the differences express how quickly the individual responds to the process of learning and the extent of learning with time, time, and effort specific to each learning situation
- Motivation: It is reflected by an individual's motivation to try to adapt to his surroundings, his capacity to harmonize with people around him, and the amount to which he strives to achieve educational goals in the educational system. The individual's drive to learn and grow is a guarantee of the institution's success.
- Feedback: Feedback is represented by knowing the individual's performance outcomes in the self-learning method in order to identify and correct areas of weakness and areas of strength and strengthen them in the institution in the correct and appropriate manner.

Influencing factors in Hotagogia

Many elements influence Hotagogia among university educational leaders, including organizational issues, personal factors, social aspects, administrative considerations, and cultural factors. And its vagueness, resistance to change, dominant organizational culture and shared values, low motivation and morale, lack of material and moral incentives, and acquired trends and ideas (Rabaa, 2003).

Hotagogia in Jordanian Universities

Hotagogia is one of the most important modern learning methods that emerged in the Middle Ages, which assists educational leaders in learning on their own, knowing how to learn, and employing learning skills very effectively aimed at achieving general goals at all levels, which contributes to the individual's development in all its personal, cognitive, cultural, and moral aspects. And the possession of modern tactics that allow him to keep up with the pace of development and change in educational settings (Obeidat, 2003).

When practicing theology, educational leaders in universities play numerous roles, since these responsibilities are included in the list of priorities that must be focused on and made from the everyday practices sought by educational leaders. In order to advance, the educational leader seeks to be oriented first to himself and then to others. It seeks to identify tendencies and desires, as well as to form modern and developed trends towards self-learning, and assists others in practicing it within the requirements of the work environment, and the practice of Hotagogia helps to expand the circle of human relations, allowing the individual to be immersed and integrated in the work environment, making him feel comfortable. And comfort that leads to self-awareness and understanding of its requirements and needs (Bail, 2017).

The study believes that educational leaders in Jordanian universities require a permanent and ongoing need to practice self-learning and use it in all educational practices, and to make it a goal that everyone strives for relentlessly, without hesitation or difficulty. Being considered the best method among educational methods used, because it measures the individual's motivation in accepting this method, as well as the amount of motivation that he possesses and can use in developing his latent skills and abilities, all of which are in the service of the educational process in Jordanian universities. As a result, educational leaders in universities must have a Hotagogia because they are the foundation for any development and progress in society, in order to bring the educational and administrative system to a high level of progress, sophistication, and creativity, according to clear and specific international standards in universities.

There are many studies that dealt with the topic of Hotagogia, which are arranged in chronological order from the oldest to the most recent

(Jayawardena et al, 2017) investigated secondary school science instructors' practices for developing educational accomplishment and how these practices link to students' self-learning. I employed the case study technique of an American high school science instructor. Data was gathered through class observations and a semi-structured interview. It was discovered that the teacher employed a variety of practices to assist his students in developing their self-learning characteristics, such as goal planning, modelling, and developing learner independence. However, teaching practices that promote self-learning, such as problem solving and critical thinking, were not prevalent in his classroom. They attributed this to the fact that the extensive content of science curricula, combined with limited resources, made it difficult for teachers to employ teaching practices that promote and foster self-learning.

Al-Shafai (Shafai, 2018) did a study to find methodological and non-systematic techniques that assist teachers in learning new abilities and developing their educational and teaching talents. The study sample consisted of (36) instructors, and the methods of personal interview and case study were applied. The availability of opportunities for learning in the place of science and reducing the effort exerted by teachers to obtain what is new in their field of work, as well as the fact that teachers' professional development must be commensurate with the design and development of educational curricula in accordance with the most recent developments in order to integrate the educational process.

Muhammad and colleagues (2019) conducted a study to determine the reality of students' acquisition of self-learning methodologies and the difficulties they confront. The analytical descriptive approach was applied on the sample of (50) male and female students. The process of computer-assisted self-learning reached a medium level, and students' use of libraries and benefiting from them through self-learning reached a moderate level, and there are individual differences according to the variables of the study in the computer axis in terms of type, and there are differences in students' responses to the variable of frequenting libraries due to specialisation.

The fourth study (2020) sought to ascertain the effect of online education in fostering self-learning among Zarqa Private University students in light of the spread of the Corona epidemic from their perspective. As there is a statistically significant beneficial link between remote education and self-learning, distance and self-learning came to a medium degree.

Commenting on previous studies

To the best of the researcher's knowledge, no study has explicitly addressed the topic of Hotagogia among educational leaders in Jordanian universities: ideas for improvement and activation. It should be noted that previous studies implicitly dealt with the main variable of the study (Hotagogia), but their objectives, sample, community, and countries in which the study was conducted differ from the country and location of the current study, in addition to its objectives such as the study of Al-Raba'a (2020), and these studies have been used to develop The tool for collecting information, identifying its results, and comparing them to the results of the current research. As a result, the current study differs from prior studies in that it investigated the Hotagogia of educational leaders in Jordanian universities: ideas for reform and activation for the upcoming academic year (2023/2023).

The study problem

Universities require educational leaders with effective competence to advance the educational process and achieve its expected goals, and they must keep pace with the changes occurring in their environment, as well as the universities' efforts to join the procession of knowledge and the information revolution that has occurred in the current era.

And, based on the researcher Waqah's observations of Hotagogia in Jordanian universities, it was discovered that Jordanian universities differ in the extent of Hotagogia practice and application, due to different levels of motivation and morale, the presence of individual

differences, the university educational environment, the organizational culture, and the adaptation to the developments that occurred, and many studies have unanimously agreed. Despite variances in the extent to which universities use the Hotagogia of educational leaders, such as the fourth research (2020), the study came to know the Hotagogia of educational leaders in Jordanian universities: ideas for reform and activation.

Study Questions

The study sought to answer the following question:

- **The first question is: from the perspective of faculty members, what are the concepts for enhancing and activating the Hotagogia of educational leaders in Jordanian universities?**

Significance of the Study

The following points are predicted to benefit from the findings of this study:

- University presidents, as it will provide input on recommendations to strengthen and activate the Hotagogia of educational leaders in Jordanian institutions, thereby assisting them in achieving the overall aims of universities.
- Educational leaders, because they will have access to latest research whose findings and recommendations can be used to attain goals, accept modern modifications, and acquire modern trends.
- Educational researchers, because they will have a valuable reference to carry out comparable studies on the same issue that can be referred to at any moment to enrich their studies.

Objectives of the Study

The following were the objectives of this study:

- To identify recommendations for improving and activating the Hotagogia of Jordanian educational leaders in order to determine the extent to which they are used in universities

Definition of Terms

- The study includes the following terms:
 - Hotagogia is defined as "an environment in which the learner can craft his goals, learning path, and determine the final results" (Al-Omari and Al-Moumani, 91, 2018). In this study, Hotagogia is defined procedurally as the degree to which respondents score on the study tool developed by the researcher to assess recommendations for developing and activating Hotagogia among educational leaders in Jordanian universities from the perspective of faculty members.

Limitations of the Study

The results of the study are determined in the light of the following limits:

- **Limitation in terms of the objective:** The scope of this study was restricted to locating the Hotagogia of educational leaders in Jordanian universities in order to formulate enhancement suggestions.
- **The constraints imposed by humanity:** This study was restricted to a cross-section of the teaching staff at three universities in Jordan: Yarmouk University, Science and Technology; Al-Balqa Applied University; and Irbid National University.
- **Spatial limitation:** The research was conducted at colleges and universities that are situated within the Irbid governorate's boundaries.
- **Time limitation:** The academic year 2022–2023 was the one during which this study was carried out.

Study determinants

The possibility of generalizing the results of this study is determined by the psychometric characteristics of its tools (characteristics of validity and reliability).

Method and Procedures

- **Study methodology:** The qualitative method was used.
- **Study population:** The study population consisted of all faculty members in Jordanian universities in Irbid governorate for the academic year 2022/2023, whose number is (2399) faculty members, according to higher education statistics for the academic year 2021 AD.

The Study Sample

- The researcher selected a random sample of (20) faculty members in the universities located in Irbid governorate to conduct interviews with them to answer the study question.
- The study instruments: Questions were developed to conduct interviews with a sample of (20) faculty members in Jordanian universities in Irbid governorate, to reveal proposals for improving and activating the Hotagogia of educational leaders in Jordanian universities from the faculty members' point of view.

Study variables

- The study included the following variables:
 - The main variables: Hotagogia among educational leaders in Jordanian universities.

Statistical Methods and Treatments

- To answer the study question, a series of interviews were conducted with faculty members, and then the content of these interviews was analyzed and frequencies and percentages were extracted.

Study results and discussion

To answer the study question, which states:

"What are the proposals for improving and activating Hotagogia among educational leaders in Jordanian universities from the point of view of faculty members?"

In order to provide a solution to this question, the information that was gathered during interviews with twenty faculty members working at universities in the Irbid governorate was analyzed. They were picked on purpose, with the goal of ensuring that every university is well represented by contributing five students each. The information contained in the paragraph was used as the unit of analysis, and after coding and assembling the responses, the researcher came up with some suggestions to enhance and activate Hotagogia among educational leaders in Jordanian universities. These suggestions are as follows:

- 1) The first proposal: adopting techniques to improve the fundamental skills and capacities that are innate in all educational leaders working within the educational system in universities: This suggestion was given by eighteen faculty members who participated in the interview sample, which constitutes ninety percent of the sample. The researcher attributes the emergence of this proposal in the first place to the fact that there is a deficiency in satisfying the fundamental needs, motivations, and desires, and that university environments lack modern educational methods to raise the morale of workers, and that they do not pay sufficient attention to self-learning in the correct way, and that there is a lack of opportunity to understand and realize the characteristics and features that can be unique to the individual from o
- 2) The second proposal: the activation of modern methods as well as methods that place an emphasis on the significance of self-discovery and the capacity to practice self-management and apply it towards creative endeavors: In one form or another, this suggestion was voiced by seventeen of the individuals interviewed, which accounts for eighty-five percent of the sample. Where they see that there is a low level of development of the self-concept, as all goals focus on the group while giving the individual a value, but it is not sufficient in a way that achieves himself, and that the leaders lack the activation of self-management because of their focus on the common goals of the group, as well as a lack of interest in universities; where they see that there is a low level of development of the self-concept; where they see that there is a low level of This results in educational leaders having a sense that they are not fully realizing their potential, and as a result, they have a low degree of desire towards learning in all of its forms.

- 3) The third proposal is that Jordanian universities want to implement the Hotagogia principle among educational leaders as one of the contemporary learning methods: In one form or another, this suggestion was voiced by sixteen of the twenty-four interviewees, which accounts for eighty percent of the sample. Whereas some people believe that universities are not interested in cultivating self-discipline and independent learning skills, others believe that universities have a defect in the development of self-learning skills, open learning resources, and self-learning strategies. They also believe that universities lack personal development of educational leaders, which does not prepare them for the next stage and contributes to their lack of readiness for it, as well as a defect in knowing the requirements for these Stage, the weakness of their life experience towards self-learners, and
- 4) The fourth proposal is that Jordanian institutions give educational leaders the choice to learn in a way that best suits them by allowing them to choose from the following options: This idea was put up by fifteen of the people that were interviewed, which accounts for seventy-five percent of the sample. The development of this proposal may be attributed to the centralization of the application of laws and regulations, as well as the lack of flexibility that exists within it. This is because educational leaders do not have the ability to choose what works best for them in terms of methods and methods, as well as a defect in the appropriate time and place for them and in the manner that is preferred by each of them. Additionally, there is a deficiency in the utilization of research and learning skills obtained from a variety of sources, as well as
- 5) Dissemination of the culture of Hotagogia among educational leaders and all workers in Jordanian universities: the fifth proposal This idea originated from eleven of the interviewees, which constitutes fifty-five percent of the sample. The inability to keep up with the changes that are taking place, as well as resistance, may have led to the creation of this idea. Change, inflexibility in adapting to the prevalent culture, and adhering to the practical routine, as well as a lack of awareness that the Hotagogia used today needs to achieve self- and then professional development of educational leaders in universities, and a lack of awareness that this requires them to work on developing their educational skills and competencies in line with these developments and to serve the learning process in the right way, given that educational leaders are responsible f

Both the study by Al-Raba'a (2020) and the study by Muhammad et al. (2019), which came to study Hotagogia (self-learning) in educational institutions, came to the same conclusions as the current study, and their findings are consistent with the findings of this study.

The investigation leads the researcher to the conclusion that the study of Hotagogia at Jordanian universities is regarded as an essential support structure for the growth of educational leaders. This is because Hotagogia encompasses all stages, levels, fields, attitudes, and conditions that are relevant to individuals and groups. The leaders have a great desire for all types of learning, and the Hotagogia is a reflection of the overall culture of universities in Jordan, as well as the degree to which educational leaders accept the concept of change, renewal, originality, and distinction.

The following are some suggestions made by the researcher in light of the findings of the study:

1. Taking into account the suggestions made by the persons who participated in the interview sample in order to enhance and activate the Hotagogia and to reinforce it among all of the workers at the university.
2. Fostering and encouraging the practice of Hotagogia throughout all aspects of university life and activity.
3. Carrying out additional research on Hotagogia within Jordanian academic institutions and making connections between it and other factors.

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